

Temporally Coherent Quantum Electron Microscopy.

Section a: State-of-the-art and objectives.

Introduction: Coherence on the nanoscale. The advancement of electronic microchips is behind the profound societal and economic transformations associated with automation and artificial intelligence. Continuous miniaturization and complexification of electronics require measuring and understanding quantum dynamics on the nanoscale. In any realistic quantum system, random interactions with the environment erase its quantum phase and cause energy dissipation. To engineer better devices, such as ultrafast and energy-efficient electronics, quantum sensors based on correlated materials, and solid-state qubits, we must understand how to minimize decoherence. An experimental approach is necessary because scattering and decoherence effects are shaped by random environment and are notoriously difficult to model accurately in real conditions. **Measuring coherence on the nanoscale** requires a new kind of probe with ultrafine spatial and temporal resolution. This proposal will pursue such an ultimate tool **by combining ultrafast electron microscopy with attosecond spectroscopy for the first time.**

Attosecond spectroscopy based on high-harmonic generation allowed researchers to observe electron motion in atoms in real time, which was distinguished with a Nobel Prize in Physics in 2023 [1]. In particular, coherent light-wave electronic motion was explored in dielectrics, where scattering is low [2–5], in semiconductors [6–8], 2D materials [9,10], and metals [11–13], where electron scattering is significant. However, laser-based spectroscopy is fundamentally constrained in its spatial resolution by the diffraction limit. Electron microscopy, on the other hand, can reach atomic resolution in space, but until recently, it could not measure coherent electronic phenomena.

Fig. 1. Periodically modulated coherent electron pulses combine laser coherence with the spatial resolution of electron microscopy, enabling investigations of quantum coherent dynamics on the nanoscale.

This limitation stems from the fact that electrons have no temporal coherence in conventional electron microscopy, meaning that their temporal separation in the beam is random, see Fig. 1. There is no systematic phase relation between wavefunctions with different longitudinal momenta [14]. Similar to the invention of laser light, achieving temporal coherence in electron microscopy can bring an immense impact on science and technology, but now on the nanoscale, beyond the diffraction limit of light.

Temporally coherent electron pulses would allow us to investigate nanoscale electron-electron interactions in complex materials, track decoherence in Floquet-engineered systems, and perform nanoscale quantum sensing and quantum control. Such capability will be indispensable for the continued progress of material science, electronics, sensors, and quantum computing.

State-of-the-art: Ultrafast Electron Microscopy.

Ultrafast electron microscopy combines the spatial resolution of electron microscopes with the temporal resolution of femtosecond lasers. A short electron pulse is created by illuminating the electron emitter with a laser pulse. Electron pulse then captures time-frozen nanoscale images and diffraction patterns of materials undergoing ultrafast transformations of laser-excited samples [15–17] and the amplitude of near-fields on the sample [18]. More recently, phase-sensitive measurement became available. Electron and laser beams are crossed on a modulation element [19–23], allowing electrons and photons to exchange energy and momenta. After free-space propagation, modulation gives rise to attosecond electron pulses, enabling phase-resolved measurements of local fields in nanostructures [20,24,25] via free-electron qubits [26,27].

State-of-the-art: Quantum path interference as a measurement tool of coherent dynamics. Phase-resolved measurements share a common principle in both attosecond physics and ultrafast electron microscopy, see Fig. 2. In so-called RABBITT [28] experiments (Reconstruction of Attosecond Beating by Interference of Two-Photon Transitions) an extreme-ultraviolet (XUV) attosecond pulse train, which has a comb-like spectrum with an energy spacing of $2\hbar\omega$, creates electrons in a superposition of states via photoionization. A subsequent near-infrared (NIR) laser pulse induces absorption and emission of near-infrared photons, creating energy sidebands via competing channels. The intensity of the sidebands now depends on the relative phase between the two quantum paths, which depends on the physics of ionization. These phase delays can be measured by scanning the delay between XUV and NIR pulses, revealing photoionization dynamics.

Fig. 2. Quantum path interference in attosecond physics and ultrafast electron microscopy. (a) Extreme-ultraviolet (XUV) pulse train creates photoelectrons in a superposition of states with $2\hbar\omega$ energy spacing that are subsequently mixed with a laser pulse. (b) Photon-induced near-field microscopy (PINEM) utilizes a similar principle by crossing electron and laser beams on a thin membrane (grey). In ultrafast electron microscopy, modulation of electron wavepacket with laser light produces electrons in a superposition of states with $\hbar\omega$ energy spacing, also referred to as free-electron qubits [26,27]. The second such modulation then produces interference, just as in RABBITT experiments. Again, by scanning the delay between two pulses, the phase difference between interfering quantum paths can be measured [27,29]. The phase delays encode the free-space propagation [27], electron coherence [30], and phase-resolved local electromagnetic fields on the sample [29,31]. Future perspectives are even more exciting, and theoretical works promise control over the scattering process by means of quantum path interference [32], realizing laser-like spectroscopy via free-electron-bound-electron resonant interaction (FEBERI) [33] and correlated electron-photon quantum sensing [34,35].

State-of-the-art: Problem. The proof-of-principle experiments on quantum phase interference discussed above push the setup's capabilities to their utmost limits. This circumstance severely limits the range of applications. The bottleneck arises in the regions of the microscope with high electron beam density create explosive Coulomb repulsion and Boersch effects that result in a complete loss of temporal coherence and spatiotemporal beam broadening. For example, to avoid strong Coulomb effects between electrons in the gun region and at beam crossovers while using limiting, e.g., condenser apertures, the electron current must be cut to below 0.1 electrons per pulse at the sample [36,37]. Furthermore, even then, the electron pulses are only weakly coherent: the usual statistical pulse duration of around 200 fs is much longer than the coherence of individual electrons, which does not exceed a few femtoseconds due to the scattering of low-energy photoelectrons [38].

Fig. 3. Single- and multi-electron pulses. (a, b) State-of-the-art sources produce electron pulses with long separation in time. (c) To coherently build up an excitation in the sample with electrons and to probe its decoherence, we need electrons that are closely packed in time such that their temporal separation is smaller than the system's coherence time.

Similarly, in the continuous-wave approach [25], Fig. 3b, the average time between electrons is on the order of nanoseconds. This is much larger than the decoherence time of most electronic excitations in matter and does not allow for a coherent buildup of excitation in the sample or investigation of its decoherence. To realize the free-electron-bound-electron resonant interaction (FEBERI) [33], short multi-electron pulses are required, with the temporal separation between electrons smaller than the system's decoherence time, ideally spaced at an optical period, see Fig. 3.

Beyond State-of-the-art: Solution. Pure electron coherence is given by the photoemission process, and ensemble coherence is given by space-charge effects and statistical fluctuations of the environment, e.g., the accelerating voltage. In order to realize the ambitious goals outlined in this proposal, as well as many other theoretically predicated effects, the pure coherence must be maximized, and the ensemble pulse duration must be minimized. In other words, in order to squeeze several

electrons into a short wavepacket, we need to a) minimize scattering in the photoemission process, b) avoid Coulomb interactions between electrons before they reach the target, c) compress multi-electron temporal envelope to below 100 fs. Here, we propose that combining the principles and methods of attosecond extreme-ultraviolet spectroscopy with ultrafast electron microscopy will fulfill these goals and enable a wide range of novel quantum measurements on the nanoscale, which we call "Temporally Coherent Electron Microscopy".

Fig. 4. Combining the principles and methods of attosecond physics and electron microscopy.

Objectives. The key idea behind Temporally Coherent Quantum Electron Microscopy is to coherently build up sample excitations produced by subsequent electrons and to measure the coherence of those excitations by monitoring light emission and transmitted electron spectra. Collecting light emission (cathodoluminescence spectroscopy, CL) is better suited to study excitons and optically active defect states, whereas electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) is beneficial for investigating plasmonic response.

Objective 1. Coherent electron spectroscopy of nanoscale objects via FEBERI.

In conventional electron microscopy, incoherent and randomly spaced electrons excite all energy levels indiscriminately, see Fig. 5a. This is analogous to doing optical spectroscopy with an incoherent white light in the pre-laser era, which was unable to measure temporal coherence. Creating short multi-electron pulses will enable the much-anticipated free-electron-bound-electron resonant interaction (FEBERI) [14,33]. In essence, FEBERI offers resonant spectroscopy similar to laser spectroscopy but performed with coherent electron waves instead of photons. The resonant interaction is mediated by the Coulomb field of periodically spaced electrons, inducing local polarization of the medium at that frequency. Electron wavefunctions modulated at an optical frequency can selectively excite a two-level system if the modulation frequency matches the system resonance, see Fig. 5b.

Fig. 5. Free-electron bound-electron resonant interaction (FEBERI). (a) Conventional, incoherent electron beam. (b) Periodic electron wavepackets coherently drive sample excitations at a resonant frequency. (c) Radiative sample excitations producing interference: Cherenkov and Ferrell radiation, SPP: surface plasmon polariton, LSP: localized surface plasmon, BP: bulk plasmon, CL: cathodoluminescence, TR: transition radiation.

Ground-breaking nature of FEBERI. Scattering with temporally coherent particle beams is an almost entirely unexplored direction, both experimentally and theoretically, because until recently, such sources were not available. From a handful of theoretical predictions [14,33,39], we expect that most of our intuitions from regular incoherent scattering theory completely break down. For example, the total transition probability is nonlinear with the number of electrons and depends on the target quantum phase as well as on the phases of the incoming electrons. Moreover, unlike photons, electrons carry charge and mass, allowing one to probe a much broader range of matter excitations, same-symmetry, and optically dark transitions, see Fig. 5c. Therefore, investigation of FEBERI offers a fundamentally new spectroscopic principle, which can become indispensable for future electronics and sensing on the nanoscale.

Specific Objectives. SO1.1: Creating laser-like Coulomb fields. In order to realize FEBERI, one has to create dense electron pulse trains with ca. 10 electrons in a pulse. Figure 6a shows the probability density of such an electron pulse train, and Fig. 6b shows the longitudinal Coulomb field exerted on the sample as the electrons pass through it. The recipe for creating such pulses and the simulation details will be outlined in the Methods section. Most importantly, we see in Fig. 6 that this longitudinal electric field is very similar to a laser field and can induce resonant excitations in the sample.

Fig. 6. (a) Simulation of 10-electron attosecond pulse train at 30 keV. (b) Longitudinal Coulomb field produced by this train at a radial distance of 1 Å. (c) Measurement schematic: PINEM electron modulation produces pulse trains, which trigger coherent emission from the sample, encoding coherence of the sample excitation. Emission is measured with a reference in Hong-Ou-Mandel interference.

SO1.2: Nonlinear cathodoluminescence. For these proof-of-principle experiments, we will test several bright cathodoluminescent (CL) emitters that have the best potential for observing coherent superradiance. In these experiments, electrons primarily excite bulk plasmons. Nonlinear enhancement is expected as the periodically triggered local field of these bulk plasmons will resonantly drive luminescent band gap or excitonic transitions. First, bright Ce:YAG scintillating crystals will be used to test the nonlinear enhancement of the CL signal with 1) the number of electrons in a modulated pulse train and 2) its deviation from the theoretical $\sim N^2$ dependence due to decoherence. This will constitute the first experimental proof of FEBERI. Second, we will explore those effects in WSe₂, materials with strong and long-lived (100-fs) excitons that exhibit signatures of Rabi splitting even under a continuous electron beam [40]. The third candidate for FEBERI that we will explore is lead-halide perovskite quantum dots, for which superfluorescence was recently reported [41].

SO1.3: Dependence on the environment. We will then study how the local environment can affect the nonlinear CL spectrum and intensity, revealing decoherence mechanisms. In particular, we will explore defect states that facilitate the increase of the coherent lifetime.

SO1.4: HOM interference with nonlinear CL. By interfering the CL signal with an attenuated laser light and moving the relative delays, we will measure its degree of coherence and its spectral phase in a Hong-Ou-Mandel interference schematic [42], see Fig. 6c. A similar CL detection scheme has been recently proposed in [43]. This will allow us to measure the quantum statistics and coherence of emitted light and, thereby, the coherence and correlations of emitting quasi-particles.

Impact of FEBERI on fundamental science and technology. Demonstration of FEBERI will open the perspective of label- and damage-free spectroscopy of individual atoms, i.e., laser-like spectroscopy with atomic resolution. Such technology will greatly enhance current incoherent correlative CL measurements of nanoelectronics, correlated materials and structural biology. Our fundamental investigation will be carried out on a technologically relevant platform, a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The planned development of the first sub-100-fs SEM has an attractive potential for electron beam (eBeam) inspection of 6G electronics, see my recent work [44], and wafer inspection beyond usual damage thresholds. E-beam wafer inspection is a US\$ 1.1 Bn industry with a 20% annual growth rate [45]. We will discuss the practical potential of our technology with the Technology Transfer Office, make sure to protect the commercially viable intellectual property, and disseminate the practical outcomes in the industry domain.

Objective 2. Measure the coherence of matter excitations on the nanoscale.

Ground-breaking nature of Nanoscale Coherence Measurements. The proposed idea will allow us to measure the evolution of the density matrix and identify the microscopic origin of correlated states in quantum materials. Spectrally resolved coherence measurement of sample excitations will allow us to pinpoint decoherence channels and their dependence on the environment.

In contrast to measuring longitudinal relaxation T_1 , measuring decoherence T_2 is much more challenging. It requires access to the non-diagonal density matrix elements. In effect, this implies that the density matrix of the probe must also be non-diagonal, i.e., **probing electrons must have significant coherence**. Transverse relaxation T_2 is responsible for the loss of the quantum phase and is usually the fastest process following the excitation of a system. Specifically, we need the statistically random (inhomogeneous) broadening

of the electron energy to be smaller than the inverse transverse relaxation time $1/T_2$. Coherent photoelectrons produced with XUV top-layer photoemission satisfy this criterion, see the Methods section. Spectrally resolved measurement of decoherence can reveal important aspects of electron dynamics that are otherwise inaccessible.

The measurement principle is depicted in Fig. 7 and detailed in WP4. First, we will produce coherent electron pulses with an energy width of < 0.5 eV. Second, electron modulation will be performed with the second harmonic to have a $2\hbar\omega$ separation in the energy spectrum. A broadband white light pulse will create sidebands, recorded with an electron energy loss spectrometer, producing interference of different spectral components of the near field.

Fig.7. Quantum path interference of sample excitations.

Modulation pulse (green) creates electron with double-spacing in energy, just as in RABBITT experiments. Broadband sidebands are then created in between, encoding the spectral phase between different frequencies of the sample excitation.

For example, plasmonic excitation in metallic 2D materials MXenes and its dissipation determines the exceptional optical properties of MXenes. Plasmonic decay produces hot electrons that play a key role in their photocatalytic activity [46]. In [47], we observed an ultrafast 230-fs excitation of lattice in $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene that involved plasmon-phonon coupling, followed by formation of deeply subwavelength nanoripples in the morphology of the specimen. Neither of these mechanisms are yet understood. It was later suggested that Landau damping in MXenes produces hot electrons that directly couple to the lattice prior to electron-electron scattering [48]. Other related studies in $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ found Fröhlich polarons [49] and possible Moiré ferroelectricity [50]. Measuring the plasmonic response of MXenes in real time and its coherence, i.e., its density matrix, would provide an understanding of the dynamics of Landau damping and relaxation. Such understanding will be the basis for engineering better MXenes with plasmonic properties tuned for specific applications, such as photocatalysis, electromagnetic shielding, or sensing.

SO2.1: Demonstration of broadband spectral phase interference. Here, we will use a simple and well-understood specimen, a 20-nm silicon membrane (Noracada Inc.), for the proof-of-principle. We will determine the degree of electron coherence via the photon-order peak shifts [30] and thus characterize the capability of an instrument to measure the coherence of sample excitation, which has to be shorter than that of the electron pulse.

SO2.2: Measurement of plasmon coherence and decay in MXenes. Here, we will use MXenes with a localized surface plasmon resonance in the visible-to-near-infrared region, such as Ti and Mo metallic MXenes [51]. We expect to measure spectrally dependent dephasing and thereby identify the most important scattering channels or resonances. This identification will be crucial to understanding the optical properties of MXenes and their plasmonic photocatalysis. In the future, we will continue with more complex MXenes that were theoretically predicted to exhibit e.g. room-temperature magnetic skyrmions in multiferroic Co_2CF_2 MXene [52], spin-polarized semiconductivity in antiferromagnetic Janus MXenes $\text{Cr}_2\text{CT}_x\text{T}'_x$ [53], topological insulation in ordered double transition metal MXenes $\text{M}_2'\text{M}''\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ [54–56].

Impact of Nanoscale Coherence Measurements. Successful demonstration of coherence measurement of nanoscale excitations, such as surface plasmons, will improve our understanding of plasmon decay and generation of hot electrons that guide photocatalytic reactions. This measurement principle can be extended to spin and valley degrees of freedom by utilizing vortex electron beams. It is also uniquely posed to measure and understand decoherence in Floquet-Engineered systems [57,58]. Upon successful demonstration, we will seek theoretical collaborations and advance toward strongly correlated materials.

Section b: Methods.

General concept and the experimental setup. Electron pulses with a temporal coherence unprecedented in electron microscopy will be produced by using extreme-ultraviolet photoemission. A temporal structure will then be imprinted on the fast coherent electrons by laser light, creating attosecond electron pulse trains. Such pulses will then be used to coherently probe electron-matter excitations on the nanoscale by observing electron energy loss and cathodoluminescence spectra. Below, we present the general overview of the proposed experimental schematic, followed by a detailed discussion of each component, supported with numerical simulations benchmarked against literature to prove the feasibility of the approach.

Fig. 8. Principle schematic of the experimental setup. CL: cathodoluminescence, EELS: electron energy loss spectrometer.

ε (nm·rad)	f_{rep} (kHz)	N (e/pulse)	I (pA)	E_0 (keV)	ΔE_{FWHM} (eV)	I_{CL} (ph/s)
10	100	10	10	30	0.3	10^5 to 10^7

Table 1. Electron beamline parameters.

In contrast to current attosecond electron microscopes that operate in the 100-300 keV range, we will work at medium-low electron energies of 30 keV. Such medium-energy electrons are much better suited to probe localized material excitations as opposed to free-propagating waves, which becomes obvious by inspecting the classical impact parameter $L = v/\omega$, where v is the electron velocity, and ω is the excitation frequency. Figure 9 shows the scaling of electron-light-matter matrix elements, proportional to the square of the so-called g -factors [18], for the free-electron-bound-electron resonant interaction (FEBERI, magenta line) and the photon-induced near-field microscopy (PINEM, blue line). Moving from 200 keV to 30 keV electron energy favors probing the localized excitations (FEBERI) by a factor of 300. Second, low electron energy reduces knock-on damage, allowing us to study 2D materials. Third, low acceleration voltage allows for a simple and versatile electron gun design, as well as a much more compact, affordable, and stable voltage supply, allowing us to seamlessly integrate extreme-ultraviolet photoemission (see the Work Packages below) and eliminate the X-ray hazard.

Fig 9. Electron-light-matter coupling strength for localized (FEBERI) vs delocalized (PINEM) modes.

Work Packages WP1-WP3 are technical and argue in detail about the feasibility of generating coherent electron pulse trains. Sections WP4-WP8 describe the core experiments and potential findings.

XUV photoemission, WP1. Conventional photoelectron guns driven by visible or ultraviolet light are designed to produce electrons with minimum excess energy, i.e., as close as possible to the vacuum level, yielding pulses with good emittance and small energy spread. However, such low-energy photoelectrons experience strong scattering before escaping the solid, and thus, there is no coherence within that energy bandwidth. In contrast, electrons with high kinetic energy escape the top layers of a solid without scattering [59]. Broadband coherence of such photoelectrons is directly observed via quantum path interference during RABBITT experiments in solids [60,61]. Extreme-ultraviolet (XUV) photoemission, therefore, has a perfect combination of properties for producing bright, short, and coherent electron pulses.

Fig. 10. (a) Compared to conventional laser or UV excitation from the conduction band, (b) attosecond XUV emission from a surface level produces a pulse with excellent coherence due to absence of scattering. Secondary electrons (SE) can be filtered with the Wehnelt bias.

XUV generation, WP1.1. High-harmonic generation technology has undergone a long evolution, and today, selecting the right methods allows for a time-efficient and budget-friendly implementation. First, 100- μ J, 1030-nm, 250-fs laser pulses at a 100 kHz repetition rate (Pharos, Light Conversion Inc.) will be compressed in a commercial multipass gas cell (MIKS1_S, N2 Photonics) down to 50 fs with a maximum 90% throughput [62]. Compressed pulses will be frequency doubled with 15% efficiency in a BBO crystal and focused into a vacuum chamber targeting an intensity of $2 \cdot 10^{14}$ W/cm², with a variable 20-40 μ m spot. XUV high harmonics will be produced in an argon effusive gas jet with a 0.2-mm nozzle. With a typical conversion efficiency of 10^{-6} , we will obtain 10^7 XUV photons per pulse. Figure 11 shows simulated [63] single-harmonic HHG spectra,

Fig. 11. Numerical simulation of high-harmonic generation in Argon.

reproducing realistic schemes in similar conditions [64–67]. Such HHG requirements are similar to ARPES experiments in terms of spectrum, space-charge limitation, repetition rate, and stability [68]. However, we need 10^4 times fewer XUV photons per pulse since the ARPES collection efficiency is about 0.01% [68].

After filtering out the fundamental 515-nm light with a 100-nm aluminum filter, the XUV focus is imaged onto the photocathode with a toroidal mirror. XUV diagnostics is performed with a retractable grating and a microchannel plate (MCP) / phosphor screen pair. Accounting for all losses, we confidently achieve 10^5 XUV photons per pulse on the cathode at the energy of 21 eV.

XUV Photoemission, WP1.2. The quantum efficiency of photoemission is proportional to the product of absorption coefficient and the photon energy: $\eta \propto \mu \cdot \hbar\omega$ and in the XUV range varies between 1% and 10% for metals [69], which is an order of magnitude higher than in the UV range [70]. We are only interested in the primary electrons that escape the solid without scattering, which account for only a few percent of the total emission. Secondary electrons will be discarded by tuning the Wehnelt voltage. Therefore, to produce coherent 10-electron pulses, we need $10^4 - 10^5$ XUV photons per pulse. This estimation is close to the parameters of HHG ARPES experiments, where $2 \cdot 10^6$ 22-eV photons per pulse produce space-charge limited emission of 1000 electrons per pulse from Cu [68]. Further, we can use empirical formulas for space-charge broadening derived for photoemission experiments [71] $\Delta E = 2 \cdot 10^{-6} (\text{eV/mm}) \cdot N/D$, where N is the number of photons per pulse, and D is the focal spot size, which for a 10- μm beam of 1000 electrons gives $\Delta E = 0.2$ eV. This scheme will yield an average electron current of 0.1 pA, surpassing the majority of ultrafast photoemission electron microscopes by an order of magnitude [36] while preserving high temporal coherence and monochromaticity of <0.3 eV.

We will use photoemission from Cu (111) Shockley surface state at a Γ point. It has a binding energy of only 0.44 eV [72] and is commonly used as a reference in high-harmonic-based XUV photoemission experiments, yielding a bandwidth of less than 100 meV [73–77]. In collaboration with Prof. [REDACTED] from [REDACTED] (Collaboration Letter attached), we will prepare a Cu (111) sample via Ar sputtering, annealing, and sample orientation via low energy electron diffraction (LEED) on the [REDACTED] station [REDACTED] following a procedure described in the works from Prof. [REDACTED] laboratory [REDACTED]. ARPES (Angle-resolved Photoemission Spectroscopy) data will then be measured with Specs Phoibos 150 hemispherical analyzer, driven by a 21.2 eV He source (VUV5000, Gammadata) or with an HHG [REDACTED] source [REDACTED]. The characterized sample will then be transferred in a vacuum suitcase to the electron gun. A native heater of the thermionic electron gun will be used for additional mild annealing to refresh the surface.

In copper, in the XUV range of interest, the XUV attenuation depth is much larger than the electron escape depth [80,81], meaning that unscattered electrons are emitted from the very top layer only. We will explore other options, in particular, the surface state of a default cathode material, LaB₆ [82]. Further, we will study the coherence of photoemission from thin gold layers via thermal evaporation of gold performed at the Center of [REDACTED] at [REDACTED] or directly on the [REDACTED] station.

Electron temporal coherence will be measured with an electron energy loss spectrometer via photon-order peak shifts, see WP8 and WP9. The EEL spectrometer will initially be provided by the [REDACTED] and later replaced with a modern model equipped with direct electron detection (Cheetah, Amsterdam Scientific Instruments) which will be sought after with [REDACTED] funding or with an equivalent program.

XUV-driven electron gun, WPs 2,4. To minimize Coulomb and Boersch effects that destroy electron coherence, we will a) avoid electron beam crossovers, b) Use large anode hole and avoid further limiting apertures transmitting 100% electron to the sample. To this end, we will use a 30-keV flat photocathode electron gun (Kimball Physics / Delong Instruments) with an optical excitation viewport. The gun allows keeping a high vacuum ($<10^{-9}$ mbar) required for the clean surface in photoemission. Flat photocathodes provide multi-electron pulses with negligible energy broadening, compressible to femtosecond and attosecond durations [24,83]. By tuning the Wehnelt voltage in the under-focused regime below 20 V [84], we will filter out secondary electrons and achieve full transmission through anode aperture. For a quantitative understanding of the space-charge limits in the regime of XUV photoemission, we simulate in Fig. 12 electron trajectories in the gun and in the spatiotemporal focus. We assume 11 electrons with an initial kinetic energy of 20.5 eV, an energy width of 0.5 eV, an initial 10-fs duration, and a focal spot of 1 μm . The cathode-anode distance is 5 mm, and the acceleration voltage is 30 keV. Pressures below 10^{-9} mbar are necessary to preserve a clean surface during $>1\text{h}$ measurements, which will be achieved with ion-getter pumps (Agilent Inc.) in the gun chamber.

Fig. 12. Calculated electron trajectories with the Coulomb effect on (blue) and off (black) in the regions with high beam density. We assume a 1- μm spot, a pulse duration of 10 fs at 20.5 eV, and an initial energy spread of 0.5 eV. The acceleration voltage is 30 keV, and the cathode-anode distance is 5 mm. The resulting energy spread is less than 0.1 eV.

In the gun region, energy broadening is only 0.1 eV if the crossover is avoided. After the electron gun, the electron pulse is stretched, and assuming a 50-fs separation between electrons, nanometer focusing is attainable, see Fig. 12b. At the sample position, simultaneous spatiotemporal focusing (with a magnetic lens and THz compressor) down to 20 μm and 20 fs is possible. This is an important limitation for nonlinear cathodoluminescence experiments, where such dense electron bunches are required. Note, however, that attosecond and nanometer resolution is still achievable at the same time with sparsely populated pulses, where individual electrons are focused in space and time but do not interact with each other, as in Fig. 12b.

Fig. 13. Photon energy effect and photon beam size effect on (a) electron beam emittance and (b) post-acceleration pulse duration.

Figure 13 shows that with increasing electron excess energy, the transverse emittance grows while the post-acceleration pulse broadening [85] is minimized. By focusing XUV light to a 100-nm spot [86] with a demagnifying ellipsoidal mirror instead of a toroidal, which can be acquired at a later stage via additional third-party funding, excellent emittance below 0.1 nm rad will be achieved.

Free-electron-bound-electron resonant interaction (FEBERI) - cathodoluminescence (CL), WPs 5-7.

Modulation will be performed on a thin silicon or graphene foil transmitting $>70\%$ of the electrons. The Talbot distance at the energy of 30 keV is 11 mm, and maximum-contrast attosecond pulses [27] will form at the half-Talbot distance of 5.5 mm. The foil has to be placed at an angle of 20° with respect to the electron beam and the laser pulse impinges at -45° , providing velocity-matched interaction with maximum coupling and no electron pulse front tilt, see Fig. 15. The required laser field strength is only 0.87 MV/m, which is easily attainable with microjoule laser pulses. As a result, we will obtain 10-electron attosecond pulse train on the sample, producing a laser-like longitudinal Coulomb electric field similar to one depicted in Fig. 6b.

Fig. 14. Generation and characterization of attosecond electron pulses via streaking on a thin membrane. The duration of the attosecond burst is extracted from the width of the streaked electron spot on the phosphor screen.

For the temporal characterization, electron pulses will be transversally streaked on a second interaction element at a near-zero angle that favors transverse momentum transfer [87]. The streaked electrons will be detected on a phosphor screen and recorded with an optical camera. Furthermore, the temporal coherence of the pulses can be measured via photon-order peak shifts [30].

Fig. 15. Calculation of velocity-matching angles between the laser (red arrow) and electron (blue arrow) beams on a 20-nm silicon membrane. Colorbar indicates classical electron energy gain.

Cathodoluminescence (CL) will be used as the main mechanism of detecting FEBERI. In particular, it allows us to use a broad range of samples that do not have to be electron-transparent and can be cryo-cooled. In contrast to transition radiation with a very low emission efficiency of $<10^{-5}$, CL produced by the decay of bulk plasmons emits around 1 photon per one incoming electron. Previous experiments demonstrated the detection of CL with currents as small as 0.3 el/pulse [88]. The current of 0.16 pA will produce 10^6 - 10^8 photons per second, in agreement with the literature on ultrafast CL, where electron currents of 0.08 pA to

0.8 pA were used for single and few-electron pulses [89,90]. CL signal will be collected with a parabolic mirror and detected with a pair of photomultiplier tubes (H10682-210, Hamamatsu), either full spectrum or via a monochromator. We will experiment with tilting the sample with respect to the incoming electron beam to obtain a better g-factor for the coherent (nonlinear) cathodoluminescence. Further, we will explore the CL emission dependence on the environment by monitoring the spectra, to measure local electronic structure around defects [91,92].

Tunable electron pulses, WPs 3, 8. Since the XUV-driven electron gun is a new concept, it may carry unknown risks. In the following, I present a risk-mitigating alternative to WP3, that utilizes terahertz (THz) electron shaping to approximate the properties of an XUV-emitted electron pulse, allowing us to carry out 60% of the planned experiments and offering seamless tunability for the FEBERI experiments, see Fig. 16.

Fig. 16. Electron waveform synthesis via combined THz and NIR modulation. An ultraviolet pulse generates photoelectron pulses that are compressed with a THz field.

Here, UV photoemission pulses spread to 150-fs duration after the gun. A THz pulse, generated in a jitter-corrected Cherenkov scheme [93,94], compresses the electron beam to 20 fs. To avoid additional electron attenuation, the THz modulation element is chosen as a bow-tie resonator or a hollow metal tube. Subsequent laser modulation then produces attosecond pulse trains, as in WPs 5-7 described above. Figure 3 shows the results of relativistic Monte Carlo calculations for a classical single electron [23], with the parameters specified in Table 2.

Table 2. Monte Carlo simulation parameters for electron waveform synthesis in Fig. 16.

τ_{xuv} (fs)	ΔE_{xuv} (eV)	$\delta E_{\text{inhom.}}$ (eV)	E_0 (keV)	L_0 (cm)	L_1 (cm)	E_{THz} (MV/m)	L_2 (cm)	λ_{THz} (μm)	E_{NIR} (MV/m)	λ_{NIR} (μm)	L_3 (cm)
10	1	0.2	30	0.3	100	0.18	50	1000	0.87	1	0.5

Notably, after the temporal focus, pulse trains do not disappear. Instead, their periodicity is growing, offering a tunable source for FEBERI experiments. To confirm this finding, we repeat the calculations with full quantum mechanical propagation, developed in [27] by Dr. Ryabov and Prof. Baum. Figure 17 shows that, indeed, single-electron attosecond pulse trains survive after the temporal focus, with the periodicity of the spikes growing along the beam propagation. Therefore, by simply moving the sample, we can tune the excitation frequency from visible down to the infrared region. This prediction will be checked by observing the cathodoluminescence spectra, which should shift accordingly to the infrared region when the sample is moved further away from the modulation stage.

Fig. 17. Tunable attosecond pulses. (a), (b) classical propagation (c)-(f) Attosecond pulses at z mm from NIR modulation. (g) Quantum propagation under matched conditions (THz + NIR). (h) Tunable pulses.

Broadband spectral interference, WP8. As outlined in the Objectives, the plasmonic response of MXenes is key to its applications in photocatalysis and governs their record-breaking optical properties, which are poorly understood at the moment. Here, we will demonstrate the measurement of plasmonic lifetime and decoherence in proof-of-principle experiments.

In order to measure the relative phase of sample excitation, and not just the free-propagation phases as in previous experiments [27], we will employ a different schematic akin more to the RABBITT experiments, see Fig. 18. Here, the first modulation will be done with a second harmonic of the laser pulse, yielding a $2\hbar\omega$ energy spacing. At the sample stage, we will use broadband white light generated from 30-fs pulses in a thin fused silica plate. This layout creates broadband interference of the lower photon energies with the higher ones.

Fig. 18. Broadband spectral interference of sample excitations. Photon-induced near-field electron microscopy (PINEM) effect on the first membrane is realized with frequency-doubled laser pulses to get a broader spacing of the electron energy comb. Just as in the attosecond RABBITT experiments, sidebands are formed when attosecond electrons cross with a laser field on the second membrane.

Below, we simulate the delay-dependent electron spectra. In Fig. 19a, we assume no electron dispersion and instantaneous material response. In a more realistic simulation shown in Fig. 19b, where material reacts with a frequency-dependent delay assuming quadratic dispersion, we see complex tilt and modulation of the sideband, zoomed in Fig. 19c. Figure 19d shows the influence of the excitation decay.

Fig. 19. Simulated electron spectra as a function of delay between first and second modulation pulses. (a) Instantaneous material response (b) with dispersion (c) zoom into sideband dispersion (d) including decoherence.

The frequency-dependent phase delay of a material excitation can then be extracted from the experimental data. Plasmonic $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes will be synthesized by MXene solution will be drop-casted on TEM grids, creating 5-10 nm thick free-standing films with electron transmission of $> 60\%$ at 30 keV.

After a successful demonstration, we will explore more complex MXenes with strong electron correlations [53], as well as other complex 2D materials, and reveal their quantum coherent dynamics.

Gantt chart.

█ Ph.D. 1, █ Ph.D. 2; P = paper, C = conference presentation, T = Ph.D. thesis.

Work packages and task description	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4				Year 5				
	Q1.1	Q1.2	Q1.3	Q1.4	Q2.1	Q2.2	Q2.3	Q2.4	Q3.1	Q3.2	Q3.3	Q3.4	Q4.1	Q4.2	Q4.3	Q4.4	Q5.1	Q5.2	Q5.3	Q5.4	
WP1 XUV generation	█	█																			
WP2 Laser-driven electron gun			C1	P1																	
WP3 THz-compressed pulses					█	█															
WP4 XUV-driven electron gun					█	█	C2	P2													
WP5 Nonlinear CL							█	P3													
WP6 Attosecond electron pulses									█	█	C4	P4	█	█	█	T1					
WP7 FEBERI CL									█	█	C5	P5	█	█	█	C6					
WP8 Tunable electron pulses									█	█											
WP9 Broadband Spectral Interference											█	█	█	█	C7	P6	█	█	C8	P7	T2

Risk mitigation. The XUV-driven electron gun is a new technological idea that has not been demonstrated yet and may carry hidden risks, e.g., degradation of the photoemission surface state. Using instead a UV-driven electron gun followed by THz compression of electron pulses (see WP8) will still yield densely packed multi-electron pulses, albeit with worse coherence and larger energy spread, allowing us to carry out 60% of the planned experiments, with the exception of WP9. We will pursue these risk-mitigating strategies in parallel throughout the years 1-2.

Expansion strategy. We will encourage and support the applicants to the ██████ Postdoctoral Fellowship. Equipment upgrade (EEL spectrometer with direct electron detection; ellipsoidal XUV mirror; a cryogenic stage for CL) will be applied for via ██████ or its future equivalent grant in the future.

Budget. All prices are calculated with the exchange rates of January 2024, a ██████ VAT of 8.1%, and expected yearly inflation of 2.1%. ██████ provides an additional ██████ startup funding, which will be used for non-eligible costs ██████. We will use free data depository Zotero and ArXiv preprints for open access.

Summary. This project addresses a fundamental gap in our current scientific understanding of quantum coherent electron-matter interaction and holds the promise of catalyzing technological advancements across the domains of quantum electronics, nanophotonics, and material science. The development of nanoscale tools has been behind the most significant scientific breakthroughs of the last 50 years. By pursuing Temporally Coherent Quantum Electron Microscopy, we embark on a journey that could reshape the landscape of modern technology.

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